

SMART HOME TECHNOLOGY AND TRENDS IN LIVING SPACE TRANSFORMATIONS

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Abstract

The improvement of management systems has opened the gate for complex automation of processes. Nowadays, technologies are developing. Similar results are also used in the smart control systems applied in houses and other buildings. In recent years, innovations in the technologies, the development process in automation systems allow to use devices faster and more productive and flexible.

Modernization of management systems in our time has led to complex mechanization and automation of production processes. By applying new and modern progressive methods, the intensification of production is ensured, thus, the quality indicator of the produced product is improved. Such achievements are also used in intelligent management systems applied in buildings. Today, technology is constantly developing. Of course, the development of technologies plays a big role in people's lives. We are living in such a time that before, "This cannot be realized, it is impossible to do." Projects using sentences like these are very easy to implement nowadays. Innovations that have happened in the field of technology in recent years, of course, have an impact on us. The development process in mechatronic systems makes it possible to use devices with faster and larger capacities. Technologies are evolving today. The results of technological development are also used in smart control systems applied in homes and other buildings. In recent years, innovations in technologies, the development process in automation systems allow using devices faster, more productively and flexibly.

The level of development in smart homes did not happen by itself. All innovations first take place within society and are shaped by the influence of trends within society. Also, with the use of special technologies to increase the value of smart homes, it is also aimed at improving the smart home environment.

A smart home is a home equipped with technological solutions designed to provide services that meet people's needs. The purpose of this article is to systematically evaluate the latest smart home literature and review research and developments in the living space and smart technologies transformations. In addition to providing an overview of the development and performance of current smart home systems and this paper provides detailed information on the latest equipment and systems.

Keywords: smart systems, sensors, electronic systems, automation, smart transformation.

The Smart Home - technology of the century. It integrates many new technologies through home networks to improve the quality of human life. Smart home commerce has attracted the attention of researchers for over a decade. Smart home technology is a combination of networks and services. In recent years, the term "smart" has become synonymous with any technology that has some level of artificial intelligence. The ability to collect information from the environment and react accordingly is a critical feature of smart technologies. Smart technology has become the main driver of innovative ideas such as the smart home system. With the development of smart products and services, the world has witnessed an increase in device interaction and data sharing, which has influenced the rapid development of smart home technologies worldwide. Due to the advantages provided by smart technologies and the possible large global market, interest in smart home technologies among researchers has increased dramatically.

In the field of home automation and control, the smart home has become a very promising sector. The term "smart home" is not limited to human residences. Rather, it has broader technological implications, including smart housing and living.

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Smart technologies are currently developing rapidly. We understand a certain concept of a computer network that connects various devices into a network; these devices interact and are able to exchange information offline without human intervention or with minimal participation. Now Smart technologies used in the industrial sector, the so-called B2B (business to business) technologies, and in the B2C (business to consumer) consumer sector. One of the striking examples of the use of technology in the space of everyday practices can be the concept of a "smart home" - a house within which the technology of interconnected "smart" things is used, which are part of the internal and exter-

nal home spaces. Such a “smart home” is a self-regulating system containing a number of subsystems: microclimate subsystems, subsystems for lighting and regulation of the operation of electronic devices; within the framework of a “smart home” a “smart refrigerator” can operate, equipped with devices with artificial intelligence, which can analyze the consumption of certain products, their stock and consumption dynamics. You can also include a security system here. It must be said that the concept of a “smart home” presupposes, on the one hand, devices that can operate autonomously in a systemic unity, on the other hand, a “house”, which is, as a rule, a separate building, they are conveniently and rationally designed, taking into account the possibility of using smart technologies. The purpose of this work is to highlight and consider some trends in the transformation of living space within the framework of smart home technology.

After analyzing some changes home space in relation to smart home technology, some trends are visible as follows:

The first trend is the increasing functionality of the home and home spaces. Configuration of living space reflects social realities is an opportunity for customized home design, taking into account both design and aesthetic imperatives, which can be unique, and functional and technological solutions. Of course, it is worth saying that we are talking about the premium segment of houses and corresponding solutions which are not available to all segments of the population, even if we take into account residents of large cities. Researchers note that only laying the necessary cables and sensors is comparable in the cost of purchasing a good class car. The popularity of individual design solutions, loft design (mainly in urban environments), regarding interior design of space is increasing. Some producing companies even say that such design correlates with the lifestyle of single people and married couples without children, as opposed to traditional design and architectural solutions of the industrial era, designed for the traditional family. As a rule, loft design involves technological equipment. It is logical to assume that smart home technologies will focus on this kind of solutions, although a traditional house, without large internal “empty spaces,” is also relevant for the implementation of the smart home technologies. The individualized design of a modern home, which applies to both the premium segment and more budget options, represents the trend of customizing a home, and many areas of life of a modern person. By customization we mean a certain trend which appeared as part of marketing strategies, it is associated with the development of personalized products and services aimed at specific customers.

Customization may imply the opportunity for the consumers themselves to participate in the creation of a product in terms of developing its features, design in a broad sense, or personalized service. It is clear that solutions in the field of the Internet of Things, such as “multi-home” technologies, require customization, since it is impossible to unify the needs and features of a home (especially when it comes to the premium segment and a separate house). In addition, customization will also concern the ability to create interior elements,

furniture and, probably, integrate them with devices within the “smart home” system (sensors, drives and other elements can already be purchased). Moreover, it is even possible to print building elements for a house and create the house itself using a 3D printer (here, of course, questions arise about the reliability of parts and their technical characteristics, compliance with building codes and regulations). It is possible that such a practice, focused on functionality and decentralized customized production, will seriously change the contours of the socio-economic system, and the very attitude towards consumption throughout society.

So, highlighted aspects of increasing the importance of the functional component of the space of the house, customization and the possibility of autonomous creation of elements of the home space.

As for the trend towards autonomy, it also applies to the devices themselves within the framework of the “smart home” concept. For example, there are already sensor networks that implement “smart dust” technology. “Smart dust” is a collection of miniature sensors with computing and wireless communication capabilities, in addition, these elements have memory for data storage and special sensitive elements for environmental analysis. These elements are comparable in size to sand grains. Each element, or “mote” (speck of dust), can have its own sensors, power supply, communication and computing node. Such motes can group together and create flexible and mobile networks, consuming a small amount of energy. “Smart dust” can be used in climate control systems and multimedia environments in the “smart home” space.

Conclusion

So, trends are identified in autonomization and increased functionality in various aspects of smart home technology. These trends echo the general vector of development of the technical and information universe in which modern people live. As information technologies develop, these trends will intensify—customization of various spheres and practices, strengthening of their functional potential, at the same time as “smarter”, autonomization at various levels. All this will concern the development of the home environment of the “smart home”, which can turn into something different compared to the current home space (if we understand the home space as a set of everyday practices). It is possible that the very principle of autonomy and autonomization of the elements of the house in its correlation with the expansion of the “computational potential” of things and objects will give rise to some new contours of human living space.

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